

PP-8 : BRIDGING GAPS IN PRESSURE ULCER PREVENTION: THE ROLE OF VIGILANT HOME-BASED CARE

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BACKGROUND:

- Pressure ulcers are a major source of pain, prolonged recovery, and increased healthcare costs in bedbound patients.
- Although often viewed as an unavoidable complication of immobility, their development can be prevented with timely interventions across different levels of prevention.
- This case highlights how vigilant community-based care can mitigate such complications.

CASE DESCRIPTION:

- Mrs. AB, a 78-year-old woman with a history of transient ischaemic attack in 2011, for which she had defaulted treatment, developed left-sided hemiplegia following an ischaemic stroke in November 2024.
- Due to impaired mobility, she experienced multiple falls and eventually became bedbound. She was hospitalised and evaluated for melaena in June 2025, after which she was discharged for home-based care with a nasogastric (NG) tube and urinary catheter.
- Her principal caregiver, an unmarried daughter employed as a housemaid, lives with her in her employer's residence, where supportive measures such as an air mattress were provided.
- Community-based care was delivered via a Public Health Nursing Officer (PHNO), including regular home visits, NG and catheter care, physiotherapy, and caregiver training on repositioning, skin care, and nutrition — all of which helped prevent pressure ulcers during early recovery.
- In July 2025, the patient was admitted to hospital for viral fever. Due to limited resources, an air mattress was unavailable, and caregiver presence was restricted. A sacral pressure ulcer was noted post-discharge.
- However, the community care team responded promptly: wound care was added to the care plan and delivered through the PHNO during home visits. The patient is now recovering well under continued supportive care. **(Figures 1 and 2)**

Figure 1: PHNO attending to the pressure ulcer during a visit

Figure 2: Pressure ulcer showing signs of healing with granulation tissue formed

CONCLUSION:

- This case illustrates how patients with severe mobility impairments are at high risk of pressure ulcers during hospitalisation. However, it also demonstrates the value of responsive community-based care in early detection and management. Proactive home-based care not only promotes recovery but also reduces caregiver burden and improves patient outcomes.

KEY HIGHLIGHT:

- Preventive services like health education and screening for non-communicable diseases were offered to the caregivers to ensure holistic care.

Figure 3: Patient assessment and brief counselling on non-communicable disease prevention to care givers